

307

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL STUDIES ON HAEMOLYSIN. PART IV. MOLECULAR
WEIGHT OF HAEMOLYSIN

BY S. S. DE

The molecular weight of haemolysin has been found to be 31,900 by the diffusion method, a value which agrees well with the values of 31,000-41,000 in Svedberg units. The value also tallies fairly well with values obtained by other methods.

There are various methods of determining the molecular weight of protein. Among them mention may be made of osmotic pressure, diffusion, and rate of sedimentation in an ultracentrifuge. The diffusion method has been used for determining the molecular weight of crystalline haemolysin (De, *Ann. Biochem. Expt. Med.*, 1944, **4**, 45) the process adopted for this purpose was that of Northrop and Anson.

If two solutions of definite concentrations are separated by a porous membrane, solute from the more concentrated solution passes to the dilute solution, and the diffusion coefficient is defined in the following way :

$$D = \frac{dq}{A dt \frac{dc}{dx}} \quad \dots (1)$$

where D is the diffusion coefficient, dq is the quantity which passes across the plane of area A in time dt under a concentration gradient of dc/dx .

Suppose a solution of concentration c_1 is separated from a more dilute solution of concentration c_2 by a porous membrane through the pores of which the solute can diffuse. The solute will diffuse from c_1 to c_2 . If the volumes of these solutions are large and the experiment is conducted for a short duration, the concentrations will remain constant.

Let the effective area of the pores be A and the effective length be h . The concentration gradient will then be constant and equal to $c_1 - c_2/h$ and the quantity q diffusing in time t will be :

$$q = D A t \frac{c_1 - c_2}{h} \quad \dots (2)$$

or

$$D = \frac{h q}{A t (c_1 - c_2)}$$

If the solution is pure solvent, c_2 is zero.

Then

$$D = \frac{h q}{A t c_1}$$

Dimensions of D.—Since concentration may be expressed as quantity per unit of volume, the units used to measure the quantity cancel out provided the same unit is used to express the concentration as is used to measure the quantity diffusing. If time is expressed in days and length in centimetres, then

$$D = \frac{h \text{ cm}}{A \text{ cm}^2} \frac{q \text{ units}}{t \text{ days} \cdot \frac{q_1 \text{ units}}{\text{cm}^3}} = \frac{h q \cdot \text{cm}^2}{A \cdot q_1 \cdot t \text{ day}}$$

in which q_1 is the number of units per c.c. of the concentrated solution. If the amount contained in 1 c.c. of the concentrated solution is taken as the unit of quantity, i.e. if $q_1 = 1$ and

the amount diffused is expressed in this unit (*i.e.* as the number of c.c. of the concentrated solution containing the quantity diffused) then

$$D = \frac{hg(\text{c.c.})\text{cm}^2}{At \text{ day}} = \frac{kq(\text{c.c.})\text{cm}^2}{t \text{ day}}$$

where g (c.c.) is the number of c.c. of the concentrated solution that contains the amount of substance diffused. For any membrane, the effective thickness and area may be assumed constant and therefore h/A is constant and may be called K , the membrane constant. In order to obtain this value, the apparatus should be standardised against a solution, the diffusion constant of which is known.

EXPERIMENTAL

Apparatus.—The diffusion cell used is shown in Fig. 1. It is suspended in a closely fitting beaker by a rubber tube. It consists of sintered glass fused at one end of the cell. The diaphragm was of G—4 dimensions. After the cell was tested for leaks, the volume of the diffusion cell up to the glass stop-cock was determined by weighing the empty cell and then filled with distilled water. The cell was first cleaned by sucking water, freed from dissolved gas by boiling, through the porous disc, with a water pump at the upper end. The liquid was expelled by applying pressure at the same end. The cell was then rinsed with the solution, the diffusion coefficient of which is to be measured through the diaphragm, and filled completely without bubbles past the stop-cock which was then closed. The cell was then immersed in a beaker of water for washing and the last drop of adherent water was removed by tilting the diaphragm and touching it with a glass rod. The cell after removal of the adherent liquid was suspended by 15 cm. long rubber tube in a clean beaker containing a quantity of water equal to the volume of the cell. The suspension was so adjusted that the diaphragm was accurately horizontal against a mercury surface. The apparatus was then placed in a water bath at 7°. The amount of solute diffused was never allowed to exceed 3% of the total in the concentrated solution.

Standardisation of Diffusion Membrane.—The membrane constant K which is the ratio of the thickness of the membrane to its effective area was calculated from data obtained by allowing solutions of HCl and maltose (the diffusion coefficients of which are known and which are extrapolated from Ohlm's data) to diffuse through the membrane for a given length of time at a constant temperature 7°.

The membrane constant K may then be calculated by substitution in the formula,

$$K = \frac{Dt}{q(\text{c.c.})}$$

where q (c.c.) is the number of c.c. of the concentrated solution that contains the amount diffused in the time t expressed in days. D = known diffusion coefficient of the substance in solution.

Diffusion cell.

TABLE I

Determination of membrane constant K at 7°

Solution.	Time in days.	Equivalent c.c. diffused.	g (c.c.) per day.	Average g (c.c.) per day.
HCl 0·1 N	0·0347	0·390	11·24	11·29
	0·0417	0·472	11·32	
	0·0417	0·473	11·34	
	0·0486	0·548	11·27	
Maltose 10%	0·333	0·469	1·408	1·385
	0·375	0·508	1·355	
	0·417	0·578	1·386	
	0·500	0·696	1·392	

Diffusion coefficient for 0·1 N-HCl at 7° = 1·88 cm² per day extrapolated from Ohlm's data. Therefore $K = 0·166$. Diffusion coefficient for 10% maltose at 7° = 0·23 cm² per day extrapolated from Ohlm's data. K from this is 0·172. So the mean K , the cell membrane constant is 0·169.

Diffusion Coefficient of Haemolysin.—Twice crystallised haemolysin, freed from salt by dialysis, was used for this experiment. Determination of diffusion coefficient was made with two different concentrations of haemolysin. For this purpose a 2% and 5% solution of haemolysin were diluted separately with an equal volume of 0·1M phosphate buffer of p_H 6·2 to give 1% and 2·5% solution of haemolysin in 0·05 M phosphate buffer (p_H 6·2). 30 C.c. of 0·05M phosphate buffer of the same p_H was placed in the beaker. Then the cell was suspended in the beaker containing the buffer and allowed to diffuse for a definite period. The whole arrangement was placed in a refrigerator at 7° and the beaker containing the buffer was immersed in water contained in a beaker also maintained at 7°. The solvent containing the diffusate was quantitatively removed and its activity and protein content determined. The density of haemolysin was determined by the displacement of xylene at 7°.

TABLE II

Determination of diffusion coefficient of haemolysin at 7°

Haemolysin solution.	Time in days.	Haemolysin diffused as c.c. concentrated solution		D (Haemolysin) cm ² /day	
		Activity.	Protein.	Activity.	Protein.
1% p_H 6·2	1·0	0·343	0·340	0·0580	0·0575
	1·5	0·514	0·520	0·0580	0·0586
	1·5	0·508	0·515	0·0573	0·0580
2·5% p_H 6·2	1·0	0·345	0·344	0·0583	0·0581
	1·5	0·516	0·508	0·0581	0·0573
	1·5	0·510	0·515	0·0575	0·0580
				Mean 0·0579	0·0579

Calculation of the Radius and Molecular Weight of Haemolysin from the Diffusion Coefficient.—According to Einstein (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1908, **14**, 235) the diffusion coefficient is related to the radius of the particle by the following equation :

$$D = \frac{RT}{N} \frac{1}{6r\pi\eta}$$

where $R = 8.3 \times 10^7$ erg deg⁻¹ mole⁻¹ ; $T = 280^\circ$ (abs) for 7° ; $N = 6.06 \times 10^{23}$ mole⁻¹ ; r = radius of the particle including water of hydration in cm ; η = viscosity of water at $7^\circ = 0.01422$ erg sec. cm⁻¹

$$\begin{aligned} D &= \frac{1.432 \times 10^{-13}}{r} \frac{\text{erg deg. mole cm}^3}{\text{erg deg. mole cm sec}} \\ &= \frac{1.432 \times 10^{-13}}{r} \frac{\text{cm}^2}{\text{sec}} = \frac{1.237 \times 10^{-8}}{r} \frac{\text{cm}^2}{\text{day}} \\ r &= \frac{1.237 \times 10^{-8}}{D} \text{ cm} = \frac{1.237 \times 10^{-7}}{.00579} \text{ cm} \\ &= 2.136 \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm.} \end{aligned}$$

The molecular weight of haemolysin may be calculated from the radius by the following equation :

$$\begin{aligned} M &= \frac{4}{3}\pi r^3 g N \\ g &= \text{density} = g. \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ [} g \text{ (found)} = 1.29 \text{]} \\ M &= \frac{4}{3} \times 3.14 \times 6.06 \times 10^{23} g r^3 \\ &= 25.4 \times 10^{23} g r^3 \\ &= 25.4 \times 10^{23} \times 1.29 \times 9.74 \times 10^{-21} \\ &= 31,900. \end{aligned}$$

The molecular weight of haemolysin thus determined is within the range of values (31,000-41,000) considered as the Svedberg unit (*Nature*, 1937, **139**, 1051). The minimum molecular weight of haemolysin has also been determined from the estimation of the various amino-acids (Part V). A fair correlation has been obtained between the two results, one obtained by the physical method and the other by the chemical method.

My best thanks are due to Dr. B. N. Ghosh for his keen interest and the facilities given to me.